

A Heuristic for the Integrated Production and Distribution Scheduling Problem

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Abstract : The integrated problem of production and distribution scheduling is relevant in many industrial applications. Thus, many heuristics to solve this integrated problem have been developed in the last decade. Most of these heuristics use a sequential working principal or a single decomposition and integration approach to separate and solve sub-problems. A heuristic using a multi-step decomposition and integration approach is presented in this paper and evaluated in a case study. The result show significant improved results compared with sequential scheduling heuristics.

Keywords : production and outbound distribution, integrated planning, heuristic, decomposition, integration

Conference Title : ICCOMO 2014 : International Conference on Computational Optimization, Modelling and Optimization

Conference Location : Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia

Conference Dates : February 13-14, 2014